

ISBN : 978-602-1178-11-9

Padang, November 9-11, 2017

PROCEEDINGS

4th International Conference on Technical and Vocational Education and Training (TVET)

Theme :
Technical and Vocational Education and
Training for Sustainable Societies

ISBN : 978-602-1178-11-9

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FOREWORDS

This proceeding aims to disseminate valuable ideas and issues based on research or literature review in the field of vocational, technical and engineering studies, which have been presented in 4th International Conference on Technical and Vocation Education and Training. This conference has taken place in Hospitality Center Universitas Negeri Padang, November 9-11, 2017.

The theme of Conference focused on the perspective of technical and vocational education and training for sustainable society to face the challenges of 21st century, globalization era, and particularly Asian Economic Community. To overcome the challenges, we need the innovation and change in human resources development. Technical vocational educational and training have essential roles to change the world of education and work in order to establish sustainable society.

Undoubtedly, TVET need to enhance the quality of learning by developing various model of active learning, including learning in the workplace and entrepreneurship. Create innovation and applied engineering as well as information technology. Improvement of management and leadership in TVET Institution, and development of vocational and technical teacher education.

Many ideas and research findings have been shared and discussed in the seminar, more than 176 papers have been collected and selected through scholars, scientists, technologist, and engineers'. as well as teachers, professors, and post graduates students who participated in the conference.

Eight keynote speakers have taken a part in the conference, namely Prof. Intan Ahmad, Ph.D. (Director general of learning and student affairs, Kemenristek Dikti) and Prof. Josaphat Tetuko Sri Sumantyo, Ph.D. (CEReS Chiba University) and Prof. Dr. Maizam Alias (UTHM Malaysia) and Prof. Ganefri, Ph.D. (Rector of UNP) and Prof. Dr. Ramlee bin Mustapha (UPSI Malaysia) and Prof. Nizwardi Jalinus, Ed.D. (Chair of TVET doctoral program, FT UNP) and Prof. Michael Koh, Ph.D. Dr. Fahmi Rizal, M.Pd., MT (Dean of FT UNP). They all have a great contribution for the success of the conference.

Finally, thank a million for all participants of the conference who supported the success of 4th International conference on TVET 2017 and most importantly, our gratitude to all scholars who support and tolerated our mistake during the conference.

Padang, 9 November 2017

Prof. Dr. Nizwardi Jalinus, M.Ed
Chair of Scientific Committee

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DEVELOPMENT OF INDUSTRIAL STATISTICS MODULE USING PROJECT - BASED LEARNING (PjBL) APPROACH

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ABSTRACT: Currently, engineering education is undergoing significant structural changes. The rapidly evolving technological landscape forces educators to constantly reassess the content of engineering curriculum in the context of emerging fields and with a multidisciplinary focus. In this process, it is necessary to devise, implement and evaluate innovative pedagogical approaches for the incorporation of Industrial Statistics subjects into educational programmes without compromising the cultivation of traditional skills. The educational community is showing rapidly rising interest in Project-Based Learning (PBL) approaches. Project-based learning (PjBL) has been found to be effective to increase student learning achievement, acquiring knowledge through active learning, gaining interdisciplinary and multidisciplinary knowledge, taking responsibility for the learning, acquiring communication skill and methods of decision-making, and also enhancing student self-esteem. The objectives of this research are to develop a Industrial Statistics module using project - based learning and to know the student's response on the developed project-based learning module. To develop the module, 4D Model (define, design, develop, disseminate) was implemented. The data was collected using interview and questionnaire. Linkert scale was used to collect data. The designed module was validated by two experts. The results of the experts validity judgement showed that they accepted the module at a very good level (Mean = 3.43, S.D. = 0.50). And The result of Validity and practicality of designed module from 5 variable were analyzed by respondents (students), in average get score 3,34 (83,53%) or practical category. In conclusion, the project - based learning module can be used for Industrial Statistics subject.

Keywords: Project-based learning, 4D Model, Industrial Statistics, Module.

1. INTRODUCTION

Project-based learning (PjBL) is an instructional technique in which meaningful tasks, often in the form of case study, serve as the context and the stimulus for knowledge-building and critical thinking. Students work in teams to set goals, acquire information, and make informed decisions. They apply the knowledge they gain through available resources like E-Book, Book and journal, their projects not only to solve the problem, but also to communicate the results of their findings. Lecturer acts as facilitators as they model inquiry, scaffold use of cognitive and metacognitive strategies, and provide resources, support, and guidance [1]. The definitions found in numerous research papers on project-based learning are as follows: 1) projects are complex tasks, based on challenging questions or problems, that involve learners in design, problem-solving, decision making, or investigative activities, 2) projects give learners the opportunity to work relatively autonomously over extended periods of time and, and 3) projects culminate in realistic products or presentations [2].

Thus, it is essential for teaching systems to help students gain new skills in both learning and using new technology into the campus. Therefore, those involved in education are required to study and find out the best ways to stimulate students to have creativity, enjoy studying and improve soft skills. However, it is found that the current teaching

systems emphasize knowledge or ability in terms of improvements, focusing on learning by heart, rather than thinking skills, e.g. analytical thinking, synthetic thinking and critical thinking. Their thinking skills will be helpful for the students when they begin to work. So, students should mainly be taken into account when considering any teaching system. The students should be encouraged to use various tools so that they would be more interested in learning. Besides, the need, the interest and the differences of any individual should be well satisfied. Thereby, the lecturers are acting as advisors who suggest to the students how to use the tools as efficiently as possible [3]. Several researchers have conducted research on various project-based learning with different level of education, however, based on the review, there is no research discussing the application of project-based learning for industrial statistics subject.

2. LITERATURE REVIEW

Project-based learning as a student-centered approach, is developing skills and content by engaging in logical tasks that involve the skills and content to be learned, have personal relevance for students, and provide real world context for learning. Project-based learning is an instantiation of education theory, research and practice in constructivism. The constructivist view considers what real people in a knowledge domain and in a

real-life context typically do, and PjBL guides students to assume a real life role and apply the tools of a knowledge domain in creating a project. Project-based learning provides a context in which students move toward thinking as an expert in the knowledge domain might think, and now it is gaining widespread interest in higher education. An underlying principle of project-based learning is that a theme or problem to be solved is established and students gradually explore the problem from different perspectives, adjust their goals and strategies to new insights gathered during the project. Student projects offer an ideal situation to provide problem-solving opportunities that present real world problems that are scaled back, it can be thought of as learning through a series of theme related activities that are based in authentic, real world problems in which the learner has a certain amount of control over the learning environment and the design of the learning activities [4]. For lecturers in particular, project-based learning has the potential to support specific learning goals while serving as an induction process that models for lecturers how they can teach children using a project-based approach. Benefits of project-based learning for teachers include: 1) Gaining knowledge across the domains of child development, learning theory, curriculum, community relations, assessment, and professionalism, 2) Learning to integrate information in meaningful ways to create similar learning experiences for children, 3) Multiple opportunities to practice collaboration while working, and 4) Strengthening dispositions desired of professional educators through autonomous work [5]. In term of online learning, some of strategies for online learning in general are reviewed with collaborative learning and teaching, particularly in project-based learning settings. The process of project-based learning with the internet is generally composed of online questions and answers, online report, online discussion by using the bulletin board, e-mail, instant message, etc. In the project-based learning, the students learn by problem solving process based on the given problem of the project. Therefore, teaching strategies such as reflection and summary of what students earn from project, and small group activity in the class which are often used in the traditional class can be more effectively occurred in online learning space when collaborative interaction mechanism are applied. Recently, educational environment and learning process are moved toward the performance centered evaluation, portfolio, cooperative learning task.

3. METHODOLOGY

This research a type of research development of R & D (Research and Development) namely 4-D model (four D models) that is Define, Design, Develop and Disseminate proposed by Thiagarajan

[6]. However, this development model is only up to the module development stage.

Figure 1, Design of Project- Based Learning Development Module.

3.1 Define Phase

Curriculum analysis was done in formulating the indicators and learning achievements as well as the concepts developed in the module. The designed module refers to the KKNI curriculum. [7] Furthermore, the student's characteristic analysis which includes academic ability, student background, motivation to the subject, psychomotor and social skills as well as material analysis done to be the basis in designing teaching module.

Data collection this research use interview technique, documentation and questionnaire. Interviews with the head of industrial engineering department and four industrial engineering lecturers were conducted to collect the information needed in the design of teaching modules and documentation techniques used to collect data in the curriculum of KKNI, Syllabus and RPS (Semester Learning Plan) of industrial engineering study program. Questionnaire technique is used to collect identification data of student's, identification of current teaching method, teaching module used and expected expectation of student in teaching of Industrial Statistics subject. The distribution of questionnaire was done on the fourth semester students of industrial engineering program STT Ibnu

Sina Batam in academic year 2016/2017 even semester. Data were collected using survey method, all students were given questionnaire. Linkert scale was used in the questionnaire; 1= Poor, 2=Fair, 3= Good, 4=Very Good, 5= Excellent. The analysis of current teaching methods and modules still can not meet the students' expectations.[8]

3.2 Design phase

Design of teaching module in accordance with the stages of project-based learning that has been determined. The design process was done following the syllabus and project-based learning concept by considering the student requirements. Project-based learning process: 1) Making questions for project, 2) selecting the main questions or determining the project, (3) reading and looking for relevant materials to the problem, (4) designing the problem, (5) designing / correct methods for solving the problem, (6) write project proposals, (7) implementation and create task documents, (8) analyze data and make conclusions, (9) make final report, (10) present final project to lecturer. [9]

3.3 Develop phase.

After the designed module completed, the module was validated by two experts in education from internal campus and Universitas Negeri Padang (UNP). The result of experts' validation shows that the designed module was valid and applicable for Industrial Statistics subject with some corrections for improvement. Then, the designed module was used in the class to get response from students about the validity and effectiveness of the module. To know the student response, a questionnaire was distributed to students who use the module. Of 49 questions, student's response as shown in the table below:

Table 1. Summary of students' response

No	Efektifness	Indicator / Achievement level			
		Creativitas	Efisiensi	Interaktivitas	Intersting
1	3,29	3,29	3,34	3,33	3,47
2	82,19%	82,13%	83,39%	83,13%	86,81%

Practical and Valid Module

3.4 Disseminate Phase

The developed module can be distributed to students or users.

4. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The results of the preliminary study through interviews with the head of industrial engineering department and four lecturers of industrial

engineering stated that: the course of industrial statistics is a very important basic course to support the other core courses of industrial engineering, the low interest of students in studying industrial statistics so that the mastery of the material in the core courses of industrial engineering are very low, and the low interest of students using a statistical approach in performing the final task and in decision making. Statistical learning techniques used so far include lectures, questions and answers, exercises, assignments and discussions in which the implementation is dominated by lecturers and the calculations are still using manual methods. Such circumstances cause the efficiency and effectiveness of learning to be low so that outcome learning is not achieved. In addition, the form of teaching materials used in the industrial statistics learning still in the form of handouts,

Power Points and statistical textbooks, such learning materials, lack attention to differences in capabilities and less support for individual and independent learning. Need assessment is performed to examine a need phenomenon of a teaching module. Respondents in this questionnaire are the fourth semester industrial engineering students registered in the academic attendance list of statistical statistics subject. The questionnaire used in the needs analysis is a collection of information to know the background of the student, the level of student competency achievement and the process of learning and teaching at the current conditions and conditions of expectation.

The results of the needs analysis obtained as follows:

4.1 Analyze of students' background

To analyze the students' background there are seven questions that are considered important in preparing project-based materials. From the results of the distributed questionnaire, 63.3% of the students are from vocational high schools, 30.6% from Senior High School and the rest coming from Islamic High School. This suggests that the right teaching module to be designed is a module that uses a more applying approach than theoretical explanation. In this case, project-based learning is very appropriate to be developed because according to the learning experience of majority of students. While the value of probability subjects that become the basic subjects of Industrial Statistics 60% of the respondents get the value of B, 14, 6% value of C and 7.3% received a D value. As for the calculus course score of 58, 5% got B and 17.1% D and the remaining values of A and C.

4.2 Analysis of Student Competence Between Current Conditions and Expectations According to Student Perceptions

To know the level of students achievement who take the subjects of Industrial Statistics tailored to the curriculum and syllabus of statistics engineering subject consists of nine questions where obtained at the current conditions only reached an average of 3,047 or still in good category, the expected competence is at an average of 4.320 or is in very good category, this means that the competence obtained is lower than the competence of student expectations.

4.3 Analysis of Learning and Teaching Process (PBM) Between Current Conditions and Expectations According to Student Perceptions

The level of attainment of the competence of Industrial Engineering students who take the subjects of industry statistics based on the opinion of the students obtained the current condition only reached an average of 3.452 or still in good category, while for the average expectation is at position 4.435 or in very good category. Of the 29 questions related to the PBM process, the categories of Presentation of the lectures of Industrial Statistics are elusive, the PBM process mostly provides theoretical and concepts, The material taught contains many elements of theory rather than application. While for the category of student expectations, the desire to improve good communication ethics in completing tasks or reports is preferred, responsible attitude in progress reporting, honest attitude and critical thinking in progress reporting and full attendance and high discipline in progress reporting is expected. This shows that students really need a method of learning that can help in improving communication between individuals, increasing the sense of responsibility and discipline in doing the task given. From the results of this study teaching modules or learning methods that can meet student expectations are needed.

5. CONCLUSION

Based on the result of research on the development of Project Based learning module for Industrial Statistics subject. It can be concluded as follows: (1) the analysis of the teaching module needs, from the point of view of industrial engineering students background, the teaching module developed should give more opportunity for the students to be able to apply the given knowledge directly. (2) The competencies obtained by the students using the current condition is lower than the expectation to be achieved by the students and expected competency by industrial engineering department. (3) the analysis of current teaching and learning process has not been able to improve the communication skills and discipline of students in

doing tasks and responsibility and create students can think more critical. This is due to the current method of studying still impressed more theories than the practice, thus contradicting the background of the majority of students. (4) the overall method of learning condition is currently categorized adequately meet the competencies and expectations of students, but to make better in achieving learning outcomes, project-based teaching module is very appropriately to be developed and used in industrial engineering department.

6. ACKNOWLEDGEMENTS

Appreciation is extended toward STT Ibnu Sina Batam, and Minister of Research, Technology and Higher Education, for financial support.

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